

26/8/1970

Mr. A. Pourmand,
Director General,
The Iranian Archaeological Service,
Iran Bastan Museum.

Dear Mr. Pourmand,

In the years 1969-1971 with the esteemed permission and advice of the Iranian Archaeological Service I have on behalf of the British Institute of Persian Studies been carrying out archaeological surface survey in Southern Iran to investigate settlement and trading patterns in the Sassanian and Islamic periods. Preliminary reports on this survey, which has not involved any excavation, have been presented to the Iranian Archaeological Service. A final report is currently under preparation.

During the course of this survey I have visited and recorded a number of prehistoric sites all of which with a single exception are located within 120 kms. of Tepe Yahya in Kerman. In view of Professor Lamberg-Karlovsky's excavations at Tepe Yahya the material from the surface of these neighbouring sites is of primary importance to the Yahya project which can alone supply the technical competence and scholarship necessary to study and evaluate the surface collections.

It is for the purpose of this study as part of the Harvard Iran Project at Tepe Yahya that I request the Archaeological Service to permit the division of these 40 bags of pottery with those from the excavations at Tepe Yahya to permit their transport for study at Harvard. The surface collections contain only broken potsherds and flints. There are no complete nor restorable pots in the collection.

On the completion of the study of this material at Harvard Professor Lamberg-Karlovsky will submit a detailed report to the Iranian Archaeological Service.

yours sincerely,

A. G. Williamson,
Fellow, The British Institute of Persian Studies, Teheran.
Randall MacIver Fellow, The Queens College, Oxford, England.

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Director General of the Iranian Archaeological Service,